

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

CORPORATE MANAGEMENT OF PRODUCTION AND ECONOMIC ACTIVITIES COTTON PROCESSING ENTERPRISE

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Abstract

Based on a system analysis of the facility as a complex production and economic system, a multi-level hierarchical structure of an integrated management system for the main production of a cotton processing enterprise has been developed as the main task of corporate management.

Keywords: Corporate governance, hierarchical management, primary processing of cotton, production, technological process, data bank, governing body, feedback.

Introduction

It is generally accepted that effective enterprise management is possible only by planning all processes and relationships of an economic entity. The main target function of planning is to ensure long-term competitiveness, which determines the strength and stability of the management object in the market.

In a dynamically changing situation in the external environment, it is necessary to improve models and technologies for managing enterprises and their groups in order to increase the efficiency of economic activities, maintain competitiveness and maximize profits. The prerequisites for the economic development of many industries indicate the need to develop new concepts of corporate management and planning, the solution of which is impossible without modern flexible approaches to enterprise development. This is due to the fact that in modern conditions of rapidly changing technologies, information support, the external environment and the rational use of limited resources, the corporate form of entrepreneurship is one of the most effective.

In the context of the functioning of corporations and the planning of their assets, it becomes possible to use the potential of integrated structures (the possibility of transferring financial resources, reducing transaction costs, the possibility of self-financing of individual business units, government orders). The main goal of corporate planning is to build a system for effective management of a group of enterprises based on the timely identification of threats and business opportunities, a system of planning and resource management within the group, as well as on the basis of the formation of competitive business units [1].

The main task of corporate governance is to protect participants in corporate relations from the potential arbitrariness (ineffective activities) of hired managers.

Corporate governance can be reduced to three main areas:

- management of property or shareholding;
- management of production and economic activities;
- financial flow management.

The main function of corporate governance is to prevent and resolve conflicts within the company, which is the key to its survival in an aggressive competitive environment.

One of the most important tasks of the state is to ensure favorable conditions for the functioning and development of the main spheres of society, including the creation and maintenance of economic or production infrastructure, i.e. such basic industries as energy, metallurgical and fuel and energy industries, agriculture, food industry, transport, communications, telecommunications, etc. [1-8].

Problem analysis

The modern economic world is very changeable, dynamic and complex, and therefore many scientists see a solution in project management. The success of a modern manager today depends entirely on the ability to manage complex (often involving many operations) and time-limited activities aimed at creating original products.

Organizations operating in certain and uncertain external environments will be regulated differently, depending on their structure and the type of management system used. It is also important that the structure or management system of the organization corresponds to the external environment in which it is located [2]. Particular attention when studying the features of managing business entities in conditions of uncertainty in the external environment requires studying the state of the organizational culture of the enterprise in such conditions. Work [2] offers recommendations on the issue of maintaining the stability of enterprises in crisis conditions.

Management of corporations and enterprises under conditions of uncertainty is usually considered as an open, non-linear, disproportionate process that has systemic properties. In work [3], the project mode with its corresponding elements is substantiated for effective corporate management: problem, goal, objectives, activities, stakeholders, schedule, risks, and also proves that analysis is an important condition for successful management informational and temporal (temporal features) uncertainty.

Article [4] presents an analysis of risk management models, their advantages and disadvantages, which showed the need to introduce new tools into corporate risk management models in order to ensure the adequacy of risk management systems to new challenges. These tools include: reframing, the introduction of real options, the use of smart contracts based on blockchain technology, the introduction of benchmarking and the approach to creating shared value. These tools primarily provide a reduction in the corporation's relational risks, but can also help reduce business risks. In addition, these tools cover various areas of the corporation's activities from contract management to assessing the effectiveness of risk management for different groups of stakeholders. The introduction of modern tools into corporate risk management models will help improve the adaptability and efficiency of corporate risk management.

In the research [5] of N.N. Trofimova, the features of modern corporate governance are considered, factors are highlighted that increase the relevance of improving corporate governance and the weaknesses of modern corporate governance. Using the proposed author's approach, based on system analysis, the basic principles, key problems are identified and the basic models of modern corporate governance are analyzed. The scientific novelty and practical value of the article lies in the fact that the author has identified the main factors for increasing the efficiency of corporate governance of Russian enterprises in the real sector of the economy.

A.D. Khairullina, A.V. Pavlova in his [6] studies proposes the integration of the risk management system and strategic management by determining the corresponding key risk indicators for each indicator of the BSC (system of strategic indicators) of the corporation. It is also proposed to improve the economic and mathematical methods used for the analysis and assessment of risks, namely: to use fuzzy logic methods (specifically the fuzzy number method), since this method allows you to assess the probability of risk occurrence under conditions of uncertainty, which is especially important for the economic environment when input the data is stochastic. Thus, the article describes the pitfalls encountered at each stage of the risk management procedure in corporate management and proposes approaches to improving the corporate risk management system.

An analysis of numerous works shows that the development of automated control systems, process control systems, organizational management systems, organizational and production systems, as well as integrated management of industrial enterprises and others is often carried out, as a rule, in isolation. At the same time, inconsistency of goals, criteria, models and management algorithms, lack of compatibility, integration of organizational, functional, production, technical, information and software, which are organic parts of a unified management system, significantly complicate the development and implementation of these systems and do not allow achieving the required systemic effect. In this regard, the stage under consideration in the development of production management systems is characterized by the integration of individual automated subsystems using a local or corporate computer network, software and information interfaces and a distributed data bank - into a single integrated system for complex automation of production and economic activities of an enterprise. Solving the issues of integration of functional, technical, software and information support forms the basis for the creation of such systems [1-8].

Methodology and discussions

Our research has substantiated the need to develop a coherent theory of management of a modern industrial enterprise, including means of describing the control object and the tasks of forming management decisions based on the principles of system optimization with the widespread use of optimization methods and various heuristics, a mechanism for expert assessments and techniques for forming decisions under conditions of uncertainty [9-12].

Representing a management object, a cotton processing enterprise, as a hierarchical structure has a number of advantages, the main of which are: the possibility of dividing the system under consideration; ensuring integration of the problems being solved; increasing the adaptability and reliability of the system as a whole; the ability to select and standardize modules focused on solving simplified problems and coordinating such tasks in a single system.

The synthesized management system for the main production, using the example of cotton processing production (Fig.) is a four-level hierarchical system, the individual levels of which are separated by the following management functions: volumetric (current) planning - operational scheduling - selection of optimal technological modes - process regulation.

The time decomposition of the production process control problem is carried out on the basis of the frequency characteristics of disturbances acting on the production process of obtaining final cotton products. Each level of the hierarchical production process control system of a cotton processing enterprise monitors disturbances in a certain frequency spectrum.

At level I, a set of problems of volumetric planning of inputs and output is solved. This complex includes: the main task is to calculate the optimal production program of a cotton processing enterprise, broken down by quarters and months; auxiliary tasks - formalization of dependencies between the parameters of the production process and variables characterizing the behavior of the technological process; justification of planned norms for the yield of final cotton products, as well as planned norms for waste (production irrecoverable losses); forecasting the receipt of raw materials for cotton modification (raw cotton assortment); optimal distribution of production resources between types of products.

At level 2, a set of tasks of operational scheduling and management is solved: the task of assigning subsets of manufactured modifications of the final product to TP; the problem of distributing available resources between subsets of modifications of the final product; schedule task, i.e. determination of the moments of the start of work (batch launches) of fixed modifications of the feedstock for cotton processing; the task of choosing the optimal sequence for launching fixed modifications of cotton; the task of promptly adjusting some technical and economic indicators of the plan in connection with changes in individual indicators of the plan, cotton assortment, equipment operating time fund, etc. A set of tasks for operational calendar planning makes it possible to increase the likelihood of meeting the planned indicators formed at level I [9,10].

At level 3, the optimal operational decisions determined at level II are implemented by selecting the optimal parameters of discrete technological modes based on the current analysis of disturbances of the processes themselves.

At level 4, the problem of direct regulation of processes (local control) and ensuring stable and accurate maintenance of the operating parameters of technological processes defined at level 3 is solved. The main

function of level 4 is polling of sensors of operating variables and direct digital control of technological processes.

Conclusion.

Based on the analysis of the issues raised, we can say that compliance with corporate governance standards helps improve the decision-making process that can have a significant impact on the efficiency of the financial and economic activities of the enterprise at all levels. High-quality corporate governance streamlines all business processes occurring in the enterprise, which contributes to the growth of turnover and profits while simultaneously reducing the volume of required capital investments.

Corporate planning allows you to focus on external factors of the company's development, since internal ones are amenable to greater managerial influence. Risk management methods used within the integrated group make it possible to reduce the level of uncertainty in predicting the course of the corporation's business processes.

Finding ways to overcome uncertainty and manage changes in the external environment remains a relevant area of management and requires close research. Thus, management under conditions of uncertainty is a systemic process focused on the classical properties of integrated management systems of corporations, associations, and enterprises.

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